

Deliverable D2.6

Evaluation of the possible funding sources

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1. Executive Summary

This deliverable aims to provide a first evaluation of the possible funding sources for the costs determined in Task 2.1 Deliverable 2.1 (*First analysis of cost elements for the setup of 1+MG infrastructure*) Input from relevant sustainable structures (RIs, Joint actions) are taken into account.

In this deliverable we start to explore some of the potential funding sources within the context of the EDIC as the model currently selected for the implementation and building in the work already carried out in the context of GDI Pillar I

- Member states
- European Commission
- Industry
- RIs
- International organisations
- Other

We will introduce the concept of Business Model Canvas (BMC), a very high level overview over the critical components of an entity's key business parameters. The BMC model has been applied to infrastructures comparable to the Genome EDIC, and shows its potential as a way to discuss and pinpoint key components.

The potential funding sources should be seen as an overview, and a first iteration. More information will be added, as more clarification can be obtained - specifically on the details of the next European framework programme for research and for the Digital Europe programme, and as more BMC's from other health infrastructures can be obtained.

The deliverable presents key aspects regarding member state funding: how to scale the infrastructure and get buy-in from a multitude of stakeholders, to whom a secure, scalable and federated processing platform will have immense value. The real question on a national level is not from where the funding should come, but who would be interested in contributing, thus establishing a stronger long term sustainable platform and distributing the financial liability of the investments more broadly over EHDS, research and healthcare.

An overall look at potential funding streams through the European Commission is presented. It describes the ambition, tools and purposes of the different funding schemes - both those that could directly support the EDIC and those that could indirectly support it through funding partnerships and communities.

Finally, we have listed a series of findings and points for further reflection and recommendations on actions to mobilise the different funding sources. For the Genome EDIC it is critical that the legal vehicle chosen for the implementation of Genome-EDIC is indeed the EDIC regulation - In order to access targeted funding for implementing the infrastructure itself.

- The Genome-EDIC should accommodate the needs of the formalised European health and life science partnerships,
- There is only limited outside funding available for the direct support of the infrastructure operations.
- There are opportunities for combining national investments on digital health infrastructure with EU funding.
- Understanding what the EDIC can offer at any given time, is critically important to manage expectations with funders and users. There is still a substantial difference in perspective across the pillars of the GDI project, in what is assumed to be achievable.
- It is urgently critical to condense the very high level use cases and user stories developed in Pillar III into actionable services that comply with legislation, and can be handled with the available data sources and technical capability.
- The Business Model Canvas presented in this report, needs to trigger discussions across the GDI project and will hopefully establish a clear path towards implementation of a business model and towards long term sustainability.
- To effectively bridge health and research stakeholders, we need to understand the various perspectives and expectations for this infrastructure. Taking this all into account, establish (develop) a viable business model and governance framework at both: European and national level.
- The GDI must identify and engage with relevant EHDS partners on interoperability of platform modules, to ensure the interoperability of the Genome EDIC SPE and the 1+MG catalogue with EHDS and to align activities and development of key features for user management and citizen engagement; e.g. Authentication tools and citizen/consent management platform.
- Engagement is needed with key Digital Europe projects, including EUCAIM, on the interoperability of federated learning services.
- Genome EDIC needs to engage with established EU level health partnerships - not least Innovative Health Initiative.

2. Contribution towards project outcomes

With this deliverable, the project has reached or the deliverable has contributed to the following project outcomes:

	Contributed
<p>Outcome 1</p> <p>Secure federated infrastructure and data governance needed to enable sustainable and secure cross border linkage of genomic data sets in compliance with the relevant and agreed legal, ethical, quality and interoperability requirements and standards based on the progress achieved by the 1+MG initiative.</p>	Yes
<p>Outcome 2</p> <p>Platform performing distributed analysis of genetic/genomic data and any linked clinical/phenotypic information; it should be based on the principle of federated access to data sources, include a federated/multi party authorisation and authentication system, and enable application of appropriate secure multi-party and/or high-end computing, AI and simulation techniques and resources.</p>	No
<p>Outcome 3</p> <p>Clear description of the roles and responsibilities related to personal data and privacy protection, for humans and computers, applicable during project lifetime and after its finalisation.</p>	No
<p>Outcome 4</p> <p>Business model including an uptake strategy explaining the motivation, patient incentives and conditions for all stakeholders at the different levels (national, European, global) to support the GDI towards its sustainability, including data controllers, patients, citizens, data users, service providers (e.g., IT and biotech companies), healthcare systems and public authorities at large.</p>	Yes
<p>Outcome 5</p>	Yes

<p>Sustained coordination mechanism for the GDI and for the GoE multi-country project launched in the context of the 1+MG initiative.</p>	
<p>Outcome 6</p> <p>Communication strategy – to be designed and implemented at the European and national levels.</p>	No
<p>Outcome 7</p> <p>Capacity building measures necessary to ensure the establishment, sustainable operation, and successful uptake of the infrastructure.</p>	No
<p>Outcome 8</p> <p>Financial support to the relevant stakeholders to enable extension, upgrade, creation and/or physical connection of further data sources beyond the project consortium or to implement the communication strategy and for capacity-building.</p>	No

3. Methods

The work for this deliverable has been performed in three stages: First a mapping has been made of key aspects of similar data infrastructures, including technical aspects like the type of data they are working with and the data volume. Second, the business models for these infrastructure were surveyed. Third, we identified financial sources for the EDIC, including sources from the member states and European funding. Each of these is addressed in a separate section below.

1. Mapping of similar infrastructures (description, scope, type of data, data volume)

1. To analyse the funding sources of GDI similar infrastructures such as EHDS, EUCAIM (EUropean Federation for CAncer Images), UNCAN (UNderstanding CAncer), EOSC, EDITH (EUropean Virtual Human Twin), FinData, HDH, the NIH data repositories, Genomics England, Sanger/Wellcome and the Danish NGC, IHI.
2. (Additionally) To analyse aspects of the incomes and business models from similar ESFRI landmarks health or research infrastructures (fees, project funds, service)

2. Business model of these infrastructures

Survey based on the Business Model Canvas methodology

3. Financial sources for the EDIC legal model

1. Member States funding. These information could be obtained through analysing the value of the Genome-EDIC platform in the broader context of health policies, health care, EHDS, policies and research:
 - a. Which parallel needs could gear the national investment towards Genome-EDIC?
 - b. Which user communities will be able to utilise the resources available?
2. European funding through funding programmes such as the Digital Europe Programme, the Connecting Europe Facility, the InvestEU Programme, the Horizon Europe Programme, as well as with the European Regional Development and the Cohesion funds

4. Mapping of relevant Infrastructure business models

Mapping a large contingent of infrastructures and analysing their funding mechanisms and business models is a complicated task, and may end up with presenting a very large paper containing very detailed information, of little utility to the purpose of taking steps towards a long term sustainability model suited for the Genome-EDIC.

In order to condense the amount of information into a workable format this deliverable presents a high level view of the overall business model of the identified infrastructures either in the form of a Business Model Canvas or as key aspects of an infrastructures business/cost distribution model.

4.1 Business Model Canvas

Figure 1 is a representation of the generic Business Model Canvas (BMC), providing the structural foundation for presenting business models of different infrastructures¹. A BMC provides a simple, visual overview about a company's strategic position in the market.

The Business Model Canvas maps out a business' key **actors**, **activities** and **resources**, the **value proposition** for target **customers** and customer segments, customer **relationships**, **channels** involved and **financial matters**. It shows **what** is provided in the centre, **to whom** it is provided and **how** towards the right, and **with whom** it is provided and **how** to the left. **Costs** and **revenues** are displayed at the bottom. BMC gives an overview to help identify requirements to deliver the services, including critical dependencies.

¹ Osterwalder, A., & Pigneur, Y. (2010). *Business Model Generation*. John Wiley and Sons.

The 9 building blocks of the Business Model Canvas

Figure 1: Nine building blocks of the Business Model Canvas.²

The application of BMC to six different infrastructures within the health infrastructure landscape is presented in the following subsections: EDITH (Europe-wide), CAT (France), NGC (Denmark), FINData (Finland), SANGER (UK), Genomics England (UK).

The following funding sources can be identified from the BMCs presented:

- Academic Research Users/projects:
 - Licencing or subscription fee - pay-per-use or annual subscription fee
 - Consultancy services to specific use cases
 - Data analysis services
- Health care users:
 - Integration with EHR systems

² <https://blog.invgate.com/business-model-canvas>

- Companies:
 - Partnerships with PHARMA and medical device companies
- National governmental grants
 - An operational budget item on the Public Finance bill to cover core costs
- Regional health care organisations
 - A subscription fee for health care users, paid for by the individual regions.
- Research organisations
 - A per project based service charge invoiced to the research organisation of the PI.
- Other compute infrastructure users
 - A “lease” model used by other data owners, to provide them with the infrastructure required to do advanced analytics in a secure environment - or to provide them with their own platform to offer this to their users

4.1.1 EDITH Business Model Canvas

EDITH³ is a CSA consortium establishing the European Virtual Human Twin (VHT). A VHT is a patient specific virtual representation that can be used for data- and knowledge driven clinical decision support systems.

Value proposition

Virtual twins in healthcare leverage advanced technology, such as AI and machine learning, to create digital representations of patients and medical scenarios. The value includes personalised treatment planning, predictive analytics, training, maintenance and education.

Key partners:

- Health care institutions, universities and research organisations: to gain access to patient data and validate virtual twin models
- Technology providers: secure data storage, cloud computing and data analytics
- Partnerships with expertise in deployment, integration and UX/UI design (User interface)
- Advisors from healthcare, industries, hospitals, engineering, bioengineering, AI and compute
- Engagement with PHARMA and Clinical Device manufacturers
- Tech transfer and innovation centres: to ensure regulatory compliance and adherence to standards.

Key activities

- Develop and maintain the virtual technology platform, including data collection, analysis and simulation capability - continuously develop performance
- Collaborate with health care professionals and researchers to identify use cases and tailor VHT models accordingly

³ <https://www.edith-csa.eu/>

- Run models through local infrastructure or HPC centres
- Ensure data security and privacy protocols

Key resources

- Technology infrastructure for data collection, storage and analysis
- Expertise in data science, AI
- Regulatory compliance and adherence to industry standards

User relations

- Provide personalised support and training to health care professionals and researchers using the VHT technology, tailored to specific needs
- Offer ongoing technical and data analysis and interpretation support
- Foster relationships through communication and feedback loops to understand evolving needs

User segments

Hospitals, medical staff, physicians, research institutions, Pharma companies, Medical device manufacturers, health care providers and individual patients

Channels

Direct sales teams, partnerships with health care organisations, online marketing, participation in industry conferences and events.

Revenue streams

- Licencing or subscription fee - pay-per-use or annual subscription fee
- Consultancy services to specific use cases
- Data analysis services
- Integration with EHR systems
- Partnerships with pharmaB and medical device companies

Cost structure

- R&D costs to continuously develop platform: data quality, volume, models, algorithms
- Approvals and certifications (EMA/FDA, MDR, CE, ISO standards, HRA)
- Clean data production and acquisition
- Infrastructure costs for data storage, security and computational resources
- Medical staff involved in VHT monitoring, repairing and use
- Sales and marketing expenses
- Ongoing maintenance and support costs

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Key metrics

EDITH have chosen to add Key metrics (which is an add-on to the generic model), in order to monitor the development of the business model and the performance of the products and services towards the value proposition - and given that this is still a CSA that has not reached the market yet.

- Size of potential market and quantification of benefits (Socio-economic, ethics usage and practice)
- Number of patients that could be supported and economic benefits of treating them
- Number of target customers and user adaptation rates
- Revenue generated from the VHT platform licences, subscriptions and services
- Customer satisfaction and feedback
- Accuracy and performance metrics of VHT models
- REturn on investment for health care organisations using VHT technology

4.1.2 Danish National Genome Center - Business Model Canvas

DNGC is the infrastructure of the Danish Personalized Medicine Initiative, operating a clinical and research infrastructure for advanced genomic analysis.

Value proposition

- NGC provides a full service platform for genomic data analytics, both for health care or research.
- The NGC platform alleviates the need for the users of building and running their own analytics platform, allowing them to utilise services on-demand and scaled towards their needs, minimising the need for parallel HPC and storage infrastructure.
- NGC provides the best-in-class security and risk management framework for processing sensitive data, which satisfies the needs of the Danish Ministry of Health as well as research organisation managers.
- Since NGC is legally mandated to collect and store genomic data from Danish patients on its platform, and offer data for reuse, any access to clinically generated genomics must be accessed through NGC, which gives NGC an unique market position.
- NGC offers a clinical platform that bundles data and analytical pipeline services customised towards clinical usage, and offers a research platform with products and services bundled towards research needs. Main difference is granularity of data, access procedure, user administration and cost recovery model.

Key partners:

- For the build up of data volume and alignment on data quality and metadata NGC depends on the active engagement of the Danish regions and key stakeholders at hospitals, for the production of WGS data that feeds into the NGC database - specifically the clinical genomics

labs sequencing samples and running them through data pipelines needed for interpretation and condensing of the raw data.

- The physicians involved in patient treatment through reference networks, as well as researchers and genomic labs, provide critical feedback on how to build up capacity, decide on data parameters etc and develop the platform towards UX/UI design.
- Engagement with Danish Life science infrastructure providers and universities is key to ensure that the platform keeps developing and aligning services and hardware investments towards research needs. In the build up phase NGC depended heavily on storage and HPC facilities operated and maintained by university partners.

Key activities

- Develop and maintain the HPC platform for clinical and research users, accommodating the specific needs of the different communities
- Build the genomic database, ensuring data coherence and quality across the clinical institution
- Build storage and HPC capacity in line with user needs and data volumes
- Collaborate with health care professionals and researchers to develop the platform according to user needs
- Maintain data protection integrity by running a best-in-class risk management system
- Maintain the political good-will of the key stakeholders at political level.

Key resources

The key resources needed for NGC to operate are:

- High quality Genomic data
- Continued storage capacity to handle the accumulation of data
- Capacity to run a clinical AND a research platform, that can support current and future user needs
- Human resources to maintain and develop the platform, service the users and protect the integrity of NGC as a custodian of highly sensitive personal information

User relations

- NGC's data is derived from patients - meaning the data is linked to a disease profile. Currently NGC has 18 disease tracks and all have a clinical advisory board attached, that help guide service requirements and data quality issues.
- NGC has an infrastructure advisory board, an ethics advisory board, and is engaged in the overarching Personalised Medicine governance board under the direction of the Ministry of Health.
- NGC have conducted pre-production surveys with user groups as well as post-evaluations from actual users, to get feedback on our service performance.

User segments

- The users of NGC's infrastructure have two distinct segments - clinicians and researchers. By far the biggest user groups are people involved in clinical diagnostics and treatment at hospital level; physicians, molecular biologists, bioinformaticians and interpreters.
- While the data and the platforms are similar there are very different needs and different risk management strategies applied to each group.
- Clinicians have rather homogeneous needs, that translates into fairly standardised services and access to person-specific data on demand.
- Researchers must apply for access based on protocols. Researchers have very differing needs depending on their perspective and experience. Some users require a lot of manual direct user support, Others are very self-reliant and care more for the performance and specs of the systems and SLA.
- Most will run their algorithms in a queuing system with many basic services being run by NGC - including user management, but some advanced users prefer full access to analytical nodes, and do their own user and data management and are willing to pay for that.
- All research users require very transparent pricing mechanisms. NGC expect to diversify their platform to cater better to less-experienced researchers
- Apart from the genomics data based users, NGC also engages with other users of the PaaS (platform as a service) and SaaS (software as a service). Given the capacity of the NGC system, its scalability and the high risk management systems in place, other users include other public health agents that for their own purposes use the NGC infrastructure as a private cloud, handling their own data, users and processing. These engagements are contract-based and invoiced directly

Channels

- Direct engagement with end-users and managers. Communication with researchers are handled through one contactpoint at NGC, which engages with the users and manages application questions, user vetting, contracts.
- Clinical users are supported with our clinical support team - particularly on interpretation
- NGC attends and speaks at numerous clinical and research workshops and conferences.

Revenue streams

- NGC has four main revenue / funding streams:
 - An operational budget item on the Public Finance bill to cover core costs
 - A subscription fee for health care users, paid for by the individual regions.
 - A per project service charge invoiced to the research organisation of the PI. This includes an application fee, setup of secure private cloud, storage and HPC usage. Other services paid for on an hourly rate include data-in services, running bespoke analytical tools and user management.

- A “lease” model used by other data owners, to provide them with the infrastructure required to do advanced analytics in a secure environment - or to provide them with their own platform to offer this to their users
- In the initial build-up phase of NGC most of the funding came from a substantial one-off grant (150 MEUR) from the NOVO Nordisk Foundation. Some external funding from the EU has been received. Neither of these form part of the business model of NGC
- Users are generally willing to pay for two things - those that alleviate their pains and those that provide them with gains.
 - On the pain side: not having to set up and run a clinical pipeline or a genomic research platform is highly attractive in order to minimise the operational aspects themselves. Users tend to want to pay for services that relinquish responsibilities and tasks on their part (Risk management, User management, Back office system administration).
 - On the gain side: NGC is the sole provider of clinical genomic data, this is the main driver for the research user's willingness to pay for services. Life science researchers in Denmark do understand that they need to pay for access, and will do so, if the funding is provided. Having a platform-as-a-service (PaaS), is attractive for the users, since the capacity of NCG's system is beyond the reach of clinicians and many researchers where they invest and/or run the system themselves. It is much cheaper for a user not to buy hardware, but to pay for using resources, (that can scale very quickly depending on your ability and willingness to pay).
- Not all users who could use the NCG platform do, in one part because of the per Project pay-for-services principle, which for researchers requires successful grant applications. For others, it is a question of not having the capacity/competence locally to interface with a complex HPC system.

Cost structure

- By far the most expensive cost, activity and resource, is the data pipeline from sequencing, data pipeline to data curation and inclusion on the NGC storage platform - it is a complex process involving many people and stakeholders over several institutional boundaries.
- The accumulation of data is a major cost driver in terms of proactively investing in scalable storage capacity. There are some indications that running a clinical platform limits opportunities to compact storage and thus limits cost efficiency, since some of the clinical users use tools that depend on fastQ data rather than more compressed CRAM formats.
- Acquiring and operating/maintaining the processing platform is an important cost, whereas the **additional** cost of analysing data on the system is negligible.
- Developing and maintaining a highly complex platform requires skills and people that are already highly sought after in the life science/compute industry - salary levels and recruitment and retention of staff are constant challenges.

4.1.3 Central Analyzer of Data (CAD) France Genomics business model canvas

Central Analyser of Data (CAD) is the infrastructure arm of the French Genomic Medicine initiative, responsible for implementing tools necessary to process and exploit the considerable volume of genomic data, both within the clinical setting and for research use.

Value proposition

The reasons for use of CAD services are a combination of:

- The data collection covers the French population tested by the two national genomic platforms under the scope of the French Genomic National Plan (PFMG)⁴.
- The data covers needs for both research and healthcare purposes.
- High-capacity data storage i.e., petabytes of data and high-performance computing (HPC)
- Trustable and safe conditions: the infrastructure follows the ISO 27001 norm, developed under strict European governance.
- Transparency, controllability, portability and interoperability across data and services
- Ability to reach a large scale of projects: digital twins, long term follow-up, predictive models using AI technologies...

Customer/user needs addressed:

- Accessing data in a secure environment
- Allowing high performance computing for both genomic and AI purposes
- Large dataset availability including genomic, clinical, and claim data
- Federated environment with other countries (data connection and processing)

Bundled products and services:

- Help desk
- Data catalogue
- Knowledge database
- Secure computing environment
- User portal

Key partners:

Partners need to cover the whole spectrum from the patient to the final usage in the medical and research fields.

Reasons for partnerships:

- Need to share data, assuming that a single partner is quite often not sufficient to solve a single medical question, more difficult when trying to answer several questions. (ie the number of patients involved in a single data centre and/or the data range available are not sufficient).

⁴ <https://pfm2025.aviesan.fr/>

- French national plans on rare diseases (*Plan national maladies rares*), cancer (*Stratégie décennale de lutte contre les cancers*) and genomic (French Genomic National Plan - PFMG)

Key partners:

- Patients' advocacy groups
- Clinical practitioners
- Research teams and networks
- Infrastructure providers
- MedTech and pharmaceutical companies

Key activities

- Ensuring the whole data management cycle, including data transfer, collection, storage, quality, processing (including HPC), data and results exchange
- Data governance including help desk activities
- User authentication and role management
- Pseudonymisation and re-identification
- Secure processing environment (SPEs)

Main distribution channels:

- Lobbying
- Community management
- Website, newsletters and social networks

Customer relations:

- Personalised customer interactions
- Managed relations to attain customer satisfaction and loyalty, "marketing" (assuming that it deals with human purposes)

Revenue streams:

- Services provided by the CAD

Key resources

- Population data
- Availability of high level medical, technical, and legal expertise.

User relations

To be filled

User groups and how they are served:

- General population, need to support the objectives (and to trust data sharing)

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- Patients, patients' family and relatives, need to consent to data sharing (and to support the objectives) knowing that the point of view is slightly different from the one of the general population
- Medical staff
- Researchers
- Governing bodies and advocates

How do you get buy-in and support from users and funders?

- National plans
- Considering both health care and research purposes

User segments

For whom are you creating value? Who are the most important customers/users?

- The general public
- Patients, patient' s family and relatives
- In the end, our main goal is to stop people from getting ill, and for those with an illness, to provide better treatment, to stop side effects, to enhance quality of life and to cure them.

Channels

Through which channels do your users want to be reached?

- Direct contact
- Digital: website, newsletters, social networks such as LinkedIn, webinars/ seminars

How are you reaching them now?

- Direct contact with stakeholders, national patients' associations, health care networks, scientific associations
- Digital: website, newsletters, social networks such as LinkedIn, webinars / seminars

Revenue streams

Normally users prefer not to pay. However, if we can provide some quality services, they could accept to pay some fee. Currently end users do not pay for services. Cost recovery is based on the French National Genomic Plan (PFMG)

Cost structure

- Computing
- Data storage
- Sequencing being performed by our partners

4.1.4 Pending - FINdata business model canvas

TBD

4.1.5 Pending - Sanger / Wellcome trust business model canvas

TBD

4.1.6 Pending - Genomics England business model canvas

TBD

4.2 Aspects of income and business models from other infrastructures

In this section, different aspects of funding and funding mechanisms of different existing infrastructures and projects are presented. The examples focus mainly on specific features that could inspire the funding source and business model for Genome-EDIC. The list is by no means comprehensive. The choice to include the topics and infrastructures presented is the author's and the author's ideas as to what could be relevant for the Genome-EDIC business model.

4.2.1 FAIR data governance - NIH data repositories and European Open Science Cloud

Why: The US National Institutes of Health (NIH) operate a Genomic dataspace based on research data that could inspire the discussion on data standard requirements, tools and funding structure within the Genome EDIC.

What: NIH has adopted a model for the reuse of research data generated through NIH grants that requires projects to ensure that their data adheres to the FAIR principles - data should be Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable for humans and machines. The same principles have been adopted in Europe through the European Open Science Cloud. For the sake of simplicity and relevance in the context of GDI, the NIH model is presented here.:

How: The NIH Data Management & Sharing (DMS) Policy, is based on a federal decision, applies to all research that results in the generation of scientific data and is funded or conducted in whole or in part by NIH. This includes all NIH-supported research regardless of funding level, including: extramural grants, extramural contracts, intramural research projects, and other funding agreements. The requirements also apply to large scale genomic data, including WGS, SNP, GWAS, variant calling, comparative analyses etc. All data sources, including genomic data are accessible to all interested parties internationally. The data is downloadable, but some sources are access-controlled - for research, only tenured researchers at professor or senior scientist level can apply for data. For other government agencies or private companies a vetting procedure applies.

The NIH requires funded projects to make available data they produce or collect, adhere to NIH data metadata standards and make a data management plan. NIH also provides funding for DMP work, ensuring proper donation and data quality, to maximise the reusability of data.

Take away: The NIH FAIR model is not directly adoptable in Europe, since no country offers downloadable genomic data, or the possibility to process the data in cloud infrastructure. The main point is that a research funder makes direct requirements on the data produced through a grant and may provide the funding for making that happen, and also provides the data platform where the data can be uploaded and obtained from. The ability in Europe to allow a similar model, depends on the uptake and adoption of the FAIR principles across European research funders through Science Europe, which could mandate the FAIR requirements and the use of the European Open Science Cloud. Many funders already require a DMP, and could support having the data donated to the 1+MG database. But this requires a careful analysis in terms of requirements on researchers to deposit their research data and the need for the EDIC to build a high quality database, which entails the ability to

reject substandard data. A deposition database is a service for scientists to upload their data and thereby honour reproducibility requirements. By default this is without quality requirements. Having a general secondary use database requires adherence to quality parameters and a legal foundation to act as data controller for being able to disclose data to users.

4.2.2 Cost distribution based on past-usage - The ESRF model

Why: ESRF operates a cost distribution model based on past usage. This could inspire the cost distribution model for the Genome-EDIC, particularly for health care usage. Health-care usage will likely have to depend entirely on free-at-the-point-of-use principle: in part to avoid contractual and invoicing blockers in a potentially time-critical diagnostic situation. Cost recovery models for health care are extremely complex nationally and very different across Europe.

What: The European Synchrotron Radiation Facility (ESRF) is a joint research facility situated in Grenoble, France, supported by 22 countries. Some 8,000 scientists visit this particle accelerator each year, conducting upwards of 2,000 experiments and producing around 1,800 scientific publications. Research at the ESRF focuses, in large part, on the use of X-ray radiation in fields as diverse as protein crystallography, earth science, palaeontology, materials science, chemistry and physics.

How: ESRF is a single site infrastructure in which users apply for access to the resources through competitive calls. The member states jointly fund the activities of ESRF through a past-usage distribution principle: the infrastructure records the users, their usage and country of origin, and adjusts the cost distribution every 2 years based on the usage per country over the previous two years.

The model's strength is that funding is linked to actual usage, which is not only related to the country size but also to the size of the relevant scientific community in that country. The weaknesses of the model are first that it causes fluctuations that the national funding agencies will need to absorb, which may be a challenge particularly if the ESRF contribution is not a stand-alone item on the national funding bill, but paid through relatively fixed or even receding research council budgets or ministerial budgets directly. Second, the model allows funders to install national caps on the application rate (for travel and other costs related to accessing the ESRF experiment platform) and thus the actual usage, which pushes the cost contribution towards other countries, who more freely allow scientists to apply for access.

4.2.3 Cross-sector infrastructure governance - The Danish NREN

Why: The Danish National Research Network accommodates non-research actors to utilise the resources built specifically for research purposes on a pre-defined cost-recovery model. This model is interesting in terms of scaling and operating the Genome-EDIC infrastructure towards other purposes than Genomics - or even healthcare.

GDI project receives funding from the European Union's Digital Europe Programme under grant agreement number 101081813.

What: The Danish NREN is a service under the Danish E-Infrastructure Collaboration, that operates and builds connectivity between the Danish universities and towards the European GEANT network and internationally. The fundamental mission is to provide high bandwidth secure connectivity that allows very large transfers of data between research organisations, either through commercial providers or by establishing fibre connections directly when needed. Having a self managed infrastructure allows the universities to scale the infrastructure at will, to set very high quality standards for data transfer (minimal interference) and to operate the infrastructure as a stand-alone dark fibre network, thus limiting the risk of foreign agents tapping into the network.

How: The five universities in Denmark are the original members of the collaboration and distribute the cost according to budgets. However over the years an increasing number of public and private entities have been enrolled into the NREN: hospitals, private companies doing research activities, university colleges, university dormitories, The Danish State Archive, The European Spallation Source and other research organisations. At some point there was a discussion of using the NREN as the backbone for a general public grid, because of its data transfer capacity, stability and end-to-end encryption model. The Danish NREN is currently the backbone of the Danish National Genome Centers' interface and data transfer from the hospital clinics.

The drive towards engaging with more and more organisations was based on a situation that created a win/win situation - many smaller entities handling large amounts of data - some being sensitive or under strict IP control required connectivity solutions that were not available on the open market. Having many years of experience and a clear business model, it was relatively easy for the Danish NREN to scale its services to include more users, thus also acquiring more members that share the operational costs.

The Danish NREN business model is open to engage with other stakeholders for them to capitalise on the capacity and resources that the NREN offers - in part to link up with relevant collaborators, but also to share the costs with other entities to whom this service is attractive.

4.2.4 Kapseli@ - Findata sensitive data platform run by CSC

Why: CSC Finland technically manages the Kapseli@ platform⁵ for Findata, which is the data permit authority in the social and health sector in Finland. The platform interface with users is managed by Findata and enables certified secure processing of sensitive data through a remote access environment. This model, which has also been extended to Statistics Finland for microdata access, is very relevant in the context of technically scaling the Genome-EDIC infrastructure and ensuring it is operated in a high-capacity provider environment and to highlight the need to provide a setup that would allow other data controllers to be included into the overall health data space. A similar model is operated by NGC in Denmark.

How: Users apply for data and SPE access directly with Findata, which will then process the application, prepare the dataset and put in place a private cloud on the SPE platform. Users pay a

⁵ <https://findata.fi/en/kapseli/>

fixed application fee, an hourly rate for data preparation and a monthly fee for a private cloud on the system, with a fixed processing and memory system. The capacity and thus price for the platform is modular and can be increased from a small to a large capacity system. Storage services are also available.

Funnelling data providers with their own requirements into the common hardware and technical management system is of key importance to ensure economy of scale. To engage with data controllers on how to engage with users and utilise data across different access regimes, being on the same technical platform will be the initial step to build the trust framework needed to supply users with data from different sources. This can be either in shared environments, through data streaming modalities or through other federated compute set ups.

4.2.5 EuroHPC Joint Undertaking - resource allocation to Health

Why: EuroHPC has within its mandate an opportunity to support health data applications in general and the 1+MG initiative specifically to provide access to HPC free of charge. Given the size of the EuroHPC HPC systems, these resources could be targeted at 1+MG edge cases requiring world class super compute resources.

EuroHPC is a Joint Undertaking established in 2018, dedicated to ensure that Europe develop, deploy, extend and maintain in the EU a world-leading federated, secure and hyper-connected supercomputing, quantum computing, service and data infrastructure ecosystem. Members of the EuroHPC JU are the Commission, EU member states and associated countries (that have chosen to join the JU) and private entities. Collectively the JU operates a 7 billion Euro budget between 2021-2027 - and is likely to continue at a similar level after this.

How: EuroHPC is a Joint Undertaking established through a Council regulation decision formally adopted in 2020⁶. In recital (44) it reads the following:

*“The Governing Board should define specific rules to grant access time free of charge, where appropriate, and without a call for expression of interest to initiatives that are considered strategic either by the Union or by the Governing Board. Representative examples of strategic initiatives of the Union include: Destination Earth, the Human Brain Project Flagship, **the “1+ Million Genomes” initiative, the common European data spaces operating in domains of public interest, and in particular the health data space**, the High Performance Computing Centres of Excellence and Competence Centres, the Digital Innovation Hubs, etc. Upon Union’s request, the Joint Undertaking should grant direct access time on a temporary or permanent basis to strategic initiatives and existing or future application platforms that it considers essential for providing health-related or other crucial emergency support services for the public good...”*

⁶ EUR-Lex - 52020PC0569 - EN - EUR-Lex:
<https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A52020PC0569>

Further investigation is needed, in order to understand how EuroHPC JU can facilitate access to compute resources under the EuroHPC umbrella. No doubt these resources would be highly valuable in terms of raw processing power, and could support the service platform for those use cases which have extreme processing requirements. Further investigation is also needed in order to understand how and if the EuroHPC systems can technically accommodate the high input/output requirements of bioinformatic analysis effectively, as well as the legal framework for processing sensitive data.

4.2.6 Summary of Funding sources inspired by other infrastructures

The following funding sources for identified parts of the infrastructure costs can be identified from the infrastructures described in the subsections above:

Academic Research Users/projects:

- Data inclusion: Funder obliges projects to make their applicable data available and the associated work is eligible for funding.
- Computing: Modular fees for usage of a specific SPE infrastructure that users are required to use for analysis of data in the infrastructure.
- Access Request handling: marginal costs for making data available are charged to the user.

National governments:

- Real costs of operation: distributed on the base of past-usage

Other infrastructures and projects:

- Computing: Using the available infrastructure for their own purposes separate from the primary goal of the infrastructure.

5. Member State funding

This section **could** have focused on the existing national funding mechanisms and sources for database and/or life science infrastructure. It could also have presented different avenues for how different countries prepare to fund the engagement into the Genome-EDIC. This approach would however have little value, in part because the national discussions are currently ongoing and in part because the Genome-EDIC has not reached a readiness-level in which these aspects can be thoroughly discussed (nor has the discussion on EHDS). Obviously as the EDIC moves towards implementation, more and more of these aspects will be discussed at national level. **Instead**, this section will paint a strategic perspective on the application of funding instruments that can work better in the future health data infrastructure landscape in which different collaborating and interoperable organisations, each providing services in their own specialty, are relevant for both research and health-care users of data.

5.1 Background and challenges

The Governance panel of the GDI project, needs to obtain a better understanding of the potential cost of the long term commitment to the infrastructure, of funding opportunities and of cost recovery models for the national investments, and also how to position the Genome-EDIC in the national ecosystem of existing resources and expected future needs, while avoiding parallel structures for similar needs - specifically in relation to personalised medicine initiatives, EHDS and other life science data and compute infrastructure.

Genome-EDIC will support life science research and the development of personalised medicine in health care, and it requires investments into capacity building, hardware, data sources, etc. in a partnership between healthcare and research stakeholders. Consequently, a lot of the discussion on funding revolves around two things:

1. Existing funding instruments for infrastructure in the life science and digital domain: either direct support funding or competitive calls; typical funding mechanisms in research
2. Health economy: Healthcare funding structure and impact on healthcare expenditures - focusing on how investments into Genome-EDIC infrastructure should be considered an investment that have the potential to support better and more cost-effective healthcare (a key deliverable in the Genome-CSA work package 3.)

Both funding avenues are highly relevant and important: for research - Which funding tools are available to support genomic research? And for health care - which cost and health care benefits would an investment into a federated genomic infrastructure provide? However, the answers depend strongly on the individual country's circumstances and strategic outlook.

What would be productive given the current state of play of the GDI project and the complexity of national engagement and funding mechanisms, is to offer a broader strategic perspective on the

ongoing national funding discussions. **Fostering precision medicine requires collaboration across many different fields of science**, in which genomics is an important - but not the only modality.

5.2 Potential synergies of investment

The Genome-EDIC is dedicated to establishing a federated infrastructure for genomic research. As emphasised in the Task 2.1 report, Deliverable 2.1⁷. The Genome-EDIC has **massive scaling challenges**. But as will be demonstrated in this section - it also has **massive application opportunities**, in terms of providing access to flexible processing and storage capacity, and as a federated secure research platform. Accommodating other users across the ecosystem built to serve the Genome-EDIC will increase the overall capacity and capability tremendously, avoid duplication of efforts and investments and anchor the infrastructure at a national level, ideally fostering long term sustainability of the platform. It will also increase the buy-in from other data controllers and research communities, to allow mechanisms to source data from different stakeholders - which is certainly in the self-interest of the genomics community.

Two concepts are important in this context;

- **Economy of scale:** Increase the output of products/services, thus reducing the cost pr. unit
- **Economy of scope:** Producing several distinct products using the same core resources, rather than producing distinct resource products using separate core resources

The high-level list below exemplifies some of the potentials that could be realised at national and EU level if there is a willingness to bring stakeholders together, in order to build economies of scale and perhaps more importantly in the context of life science, economy of scope. Certainly some of the examples will take considerable time, coordination and effort to realise, and depend entirely on the ability to coordinate efforts across stakeholders within the general life science realm at national level.

- Clinical genomic pipeline and storage facility - at national, regional or hospital level (Also economy of Scope)
- EOSC - providing a long term scalable FAIR data repository to researchers
- European Health partnership data platforms: Innovative Health Initiative, Transformation of Health systems, ERA for Health, Rare Diseases, Personalised Medicine
- Generic sensitive data Secure processing Environment
- Supporting Digital Europe platforms: EDITH, EUCAIM, EUCAN, etc
- National PPP innovation platform for medical or biomedical research
- Data space for cross sectoral and/or cross institutional research networks

⁷ First analysis of cost elements for the setup of 1+MG infrastructure; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10728049>

- Data space for clinical health registries and databases
- National EHDS integration - providing the technical backbone for EHDS, including a secure processing environment
- Clinical data platform for diagnostics and quality management
- Medicine Agency's data analytics platform and integration with EMA through the DARWIN project
- Data platform for national health biobank facilities
- Embassy and integration platform with other data holders (National Statistics Agencies, NGO's, GP unions)
- Data analytics platform for public health and disease control (pandemic preparedness contingency plan resource)

All these infrastructures could benefit from the scalable infrastructure that is set up in a country to provide a functional Genome EDIC node. This is not a full list of potential synergies that could be created for the Genome-EDIC investment, and obviously not all avenues are available or attractive to the different countries.

It is also evident that in terms of governance increasing the interdependency comes with its own sets of challenges, particularly bridging health care needs and research needs and prioritisation between differing research requirements. On the other hand, if the stakeholders are NOT forced into an institutionalised collaboration framework, it is hard to see how the infrastructure can create economies of scale and not end up being a very targeted infrastructure for a subset of the potential user base.

6. European funding schemes of relevance to Genome-EDIC

In this section a brief overview over European funding schemes is presented. Some of the programmes are in place, and are already expected to support the development of the 1+MG data infrastructure. Other programmes are targeted at potential user communities, and have the ability to feed into the Genome-EDIC infrastructure. Due to the establishment of a new Commission, it will not be expected to be formalised and in place before the end of 2024 or early 2025. The development there needs to be followed closely for at least the next year to fully understand the full scope of the funding sources available for the long term sustainability for Genome-EDIC.

6.1 New Commission's targets for health and digitization

Currently (as of end of September 2024) the new Commission is not yet in place, and thus there are no clear picture for the Commission targets for health and digitization. Priorities for those topics may only present themselves once a new Commission is established and Commissioners for Digitalization

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and for Health have been appointed. By the time that happens, the GDI project will have to make significant progress.

What can be noted from the candidate commissioner's mission letters is that European efforts to support genome sequencing and on genomic medicine should be stepped up. It is very likely that new funding possibilities will present themselves, but it is too early to have a clear picture of the format and amounts allocated for these topics.

6.2 Horizon Europe programme

Horizon Europe is the EU's key funding programme for research and innovation. Following the Multiannual Financial Framework Midterm Review (MTR) decision, the indicative funding amount for Horizon Europe for the period 2021-2027 is EUR 93,5 billion.

The programme is very extensive, and will end by 2027. Assuming that some of the key priorities relevant in the context of the Genome-EDIC will remain for the future programme (FP10) - focusing on research and innovation for competitiveness and growth, facilitating collaboration and strengthening the impact of research and innovation and creating economic growth and jobs, among other things focusing on research infrastructures, health, cancer, digitization and innovation partnerships.

A key aspect of Horizon Europe is the establishment of objective driven partnerships in support of EU's policy objectives. European Partnerships are initiatives in which the EU Commission and private and/or public partners commit themselves to jointly support the development and implementation of a research and innovation programme. They make a significant contribution to achieving the EU's political priorities, such as the Green Deal, Europe's digital strategy or pandemic preparedness.

The strategic approach under Horizon Europe aims to improve the coherence of the partnerships among themselves and in interaction with other instruments in the Framework Programme. In addition, the partnerships are to be made more open and transparent in terms of participants, activities and results.

Horizon Europe distinguishes between 3 types of European Partnerships:

- **Co-funded partnerships** involving public authorities
- **Co-programmed partnerships** between the Commission and private and/or public partners
- **Institutionalised partnerships**, based on long-term dimension and need for higher integration under the legal framework of Article 187 or 185 TFEU and EIT-Regulation supported by Horizon Europe. They can involve several Member States, bodies established through a Decision of the Council or EIT Knowledge and Innovation Communities.

The three types of European Partnerships are different from each other with respect to their implementation and certain other features. The Co-programmed are the most simple to prepare and implement, and the Institutionalised, the most complex. The European Partnerships in Horizon Europe are an evolution from certain partnership types in Horizon 2020: The Co-funded partnerships

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are successors of the European Joint Programme (EJP) Cofund and ERA-NET Cofund actions under Horizon 2020. The co-programmed partnerships follow the Contractual Public-Private-Partnerships (cPPP) under Horizon 2020. Institutionalised European Partnerships are based on Art. 187 and Art. 185 of the TFEU but are no longer called Art. 185/187 initiatives or Joint Undertakings. EIT Knowledge and Innovation Communities (EIT-KICs) are also part of Institutionalised partnerships in Horizon Europe.

For Genome-EDIC these are the most relevant partnerships in existence or being prepared

Institutionalised partnerships

1. Innovative Health Initiative
2. Transformation of Health systems

Co-funded partnerships

1. ERA for Health
2. Rare Diseases
3. Personalised Medicine
4. Pandemic Preparedness

Co-programmed partnerships

1. European Open Science Cloud

In the context of Genome-EDIC the partnerships are relevant, not necessarily as a direct funding channel, but because many of the critical user communities - researchers, health care and private companies are engaged in projects under the partnership structure. These projects will have needs that the Genome-EDIC can cater to: providing a federated research platform for sensitive data, with scalable compute and storage resources with advanced user support. Providing services towards the partnerships will drive economies of scale for the infrastructure and significantly enhance the partnerships outputs, by allowing these to concentrate on their mission by offering simple access to platform-as-a-service infrastructure.

6.3 Funding for EHDS implementation

While EHDS is very specific on general framework, requirements and usability, the regulation itself is very limited in its description of functionalities of a secure processing environment. Given the generic nature and scalability of digital resources and infrastructure, there is the possibility that an infrastructure with the capacity and capability fit for purpose for genomic analysis will be able to accommodate a considerable number of users and functionalities under the EHDS umbrella itself. In that regard, ensuring interaction between EHDS stakeholders and the Genome-EDIC will allow EHDS to capitalise on the build up of technical capacity for Genomics - that would allow users to utilise resources in the same secure processing environment, and do advanced analytics across different

data access regimes.. Not aligning Genome-EDIC with EHDS carries the risk of building parallel structures unsuited to fulfil the mission of both Genome-EDIC and EHDS.

Since the EHDS regulation is in the final stages of decision, and it is expected that the regulation and infrastructure must be implemented by 2028-2030, funding for these actions are being prepared through the EU4Health and Digital Europe programme. But this will only become official after the adoption and publication sometime early 2025.

In order for EHDS to function as a digital data space, it is vital that there is a level of cohesion in terms of digital capacity in the national health care systems, to make data available through interface with the EHDS Health Data Access Body. While the focus for many countries will likely be on aspects not directly linked to genomics, there are EHDS/HDAB components that the Genome-EDIC depends upon for a successful implementation: at least the Citizen Portal and an eID solution for health care.

- The establishment of a Citizen Portal - either at European or national level, that provides citizens with the tools to enforce their rights as data subjects - documenting and recording consents when needed, and to document data usage etc.. This is a highly complicated problem that requires a government mandate in the countries to be implemented. While the EDIC can create its own bespoke system, to honour the general GDPR requirements it is considerably better to piggy-back on a healthcare/government endorsed system. The caveat is that this will take time - also beyond the end of the GDI project, and may not be implemented uniformly across the countries.
- An eID solution that will establish the clear link between natural persons and access to resources, is a critical feature for EHDS in ensuring that data users are vetted correctly according to the data use governance and purposes allowed for to access health data, at both for health care and for secondary purposes. For the long term sustainability of the Genome-EDIC, adherence to those systems is vital.

6.4 The Digital Europe Programme

The Digital Europe Programme (DIGITAL) is an EU funding programme focused on bringing digital technology to businesses, citizens and public administrations and to avoid dependencies on systems and solutions coming from other parts of the world, to improve EUs digital capacities and limiting vulnerabilities in our digital supply chain, including investing in cybersecurity.

The Digital Europe Programme provides strategic funding to support projects in key capacity areas such as: supercomputing, artificial intelligence, cybersecurity, advanced digital skills, and ensuring a wide use of digital technologies across the economy and society. It supports industry, small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs), and public administration in their digital transformation with a reinforced network of European Digital Innovation Hubs (EDIH).

Digital Europe has five building blocks available:

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- **eDelivery** offers specifications, sample software and support services for setting up a registered delivery service infrastructure for exchanging data and documents.
- **eID** helps to set up the technical infrastructure needed to electronically identify citizens, businesses and public authorities from other European Member States, as defined in the eIDAS Regulation.
- **eInvoicing** supports the seamless generation, sending, receiving and processing of electronic invoices across borders in line with the European Directive and standard on electronic invoicing.
- **eSignature** helps to create and verify electronic signatures in line with the eIDAS Regulation.
- **Once-Only Technical System** (OOTS) reduces administrative burden for individuals and businesses.

With an overall budget of over €7.9 billion, DIGITAL aims to shape the digital transformation of Europe's society and economy, in line with EU's goals defined in the Communication - 2030 Digital Compass: The European way for the Digital Decade⁸ and in the Policy Programme - Path to the Digital Decade⁹.

6.5 EU4Health Programme

The EU4Health funding scheme is currently being used to support infrastructure and tool development for secondary use through the HDAB projects and for procurement of technical solutions. Since the European Parliament has requested that more funding should be allocated towards EHDS going forward, there may be opportunities in the programme - in particular for joint solutions.

The EU4Health programme was adopted as a response to the COVID-19 pandemic and to reinforce crisis preparedness in the EU. The pandemic highlighted the fragility of national health systems. The EU4Health programme aims at bringing a contribution to the long-term health challenges by building stronger, more resilient and more accessible health systems.

EU4Health has a €5.3 billion budget during the 2021-27 period. The EU4Health programme seeks to bring an EU added value and complements the policies of the Member States to pursue four general objectives representing the ambitions of the programme and ten specific objectives representing the areas of intervention:

- Improve and foster health
- Protect people
- Access to medicinal products, medical devices and crisis-relevant products

⁸ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/en/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A52021DC0118>

⁹ <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/news/commission-welcomes-political-agreement-digital-decade-policy-programme-driving-successful-digital>

- Strengthen health systems

6.6 The European Innovation Council - The EIC partnership programme

The EIC programme, specifically the partnership programme, would allow innovators and SME's within biotech and health applications to get access to the EDIC's data and computational resources, through paid services. This is not direct funding of the infrastructure's construction or operation, but funding towards using the infrastructure.

The European Innovation Council supports different stages of innovation from early stage research to proof of concept, technology transfer, and the financing and scale up of start-ups and small and medium-sized enterprises. The EIC uses three complementary instruments:

- **Pathfinder:** R&I grants, from early technology to proof of concept
- **Transition:** R&I grants from proof of concept to precommercial
- **Accelerator:** Grants and investment for single SMEs and start-ups, from pre-commercial to market and scale-up.

GD I project receives funding from the European Union's Digital Europe Programme under grant agreement number 101081813.

Each of these works through a competitive grant mechanism. Just recently ELIXIR joined the EIC Ecosystem Partnerships and Co-Investment Support Programme¹⁰, which allows EIC beneficiaries to use their grants to fund access to specialised services - among others with ELIXIR.

The purpose of the Partnership Programme is to provide sector-specific and niche services essential to many EIC beneficiaries to boost scaleup for (new) market entry. These new partnerships aim to fill in the existing gaps in the supply of specialised services.. All EIC Partners will undergo screening and selection by the EIC Contractor and EIC prior to onboarding on to the Programme. The EIC beneficiaries applying to the services on the EIC Service Catalogue can pay for the service (when applicable) from their resources (including grants) and starting in 2024, eligible EIC beneficiaries may receive support to cover up to 50% of the cost of a service through a cascade funding scheme offered by the EIC.

6.7 European investment programmes

The European investment programmes are interesting in the context of the EDIC and EHDS, as it provides co-funding to support the digitization of health care. This could in turn support the production of more structured digital data at local, regional and national level, that could make data inclusion into the Genome-EDIC more effective and cost-efficient and support better data extraction from EHDS at national level.

The InvestEU Programme as well as **the European Regional Development and the Cohesion funds** offer countries opportunities to make national and regional investments through different financial instruments including loans and co-funded investments. These investments are focused on increasing the economic, social and territorial cohesion across Europe, and focus among other things on sustainable development within areas as diverse as innovation infrastructure, applied research and innovation, Business support, SME's, data economy, health and health technologies and digitalisation, including digitalisation of the public sector.

In the context of Genome-EDIC these funding vehicles might not present direct opportunities for the infrastructure as such, but they might present an opportunity for countries to support capacity building at a regional level - in terms of innovation, and also in terms of digitalisation of health systems, which is likely a prerequisite for capitalising on the Genome-EDIC.

6.8 Connecting Europe Facility - The CEF Digital programme

The main element of the CEF programme relevant in the context of Genome-EDIC (And EHDS) is the deployment of new or upgrading of existing high speed backbone networks across Europe and beyond. Between 2021 and 2027 it is expected that the programme will allocate around 250 MEUR per year to digital connectivity projects throughout Europe.

¹⁰https://eic.ec.europa.eu/eic-funding-opportunities/business-acceleration-services/eic-ecosystem-partnership-programme_en

As with the investment programmes presented in 6.7 this funding vehicle might not present direct opportunities for the infrastructure as such, but it might present an opportunity for countries to support technical capacity building at a regional level needed to interact with the Genome-EDIC infrastructure.

7. Results

- This report gives a high level overview into available funding sources for the Genome-EDIC and has built a framework for discussing a sustainable business model through the Business Model Canvas method - focusing on highlighting value proposition, and evaluating funding streams, dependencies and interaction with users, all of which are fundamental to direct discussions into building a sustainable platform.
- While the overall methodology of analysing Business Model Canvases is a good approach, and a questionnaire has been produced, this report has not managed to get feedback in time, to provide a business model overview over similar infrastructures. More efforts into analysing business model canvases for existing infrastructures should continue.
- The report gives a good overview over different aspects of cost recovery, cost distribution and funding mechanisms in place for existing infrastructures, that will directly feed into the discussion surrounding the funding of the infrastructure.
- The report highlights the many approaches that should be investigated at national level in order to support investments into the Genome-EDIC, given that the platform can be applied for many health usages outside genomics.
- The report gives a generic overview over EU funding opportunities directly applicable for the EDIC - although given the timing of the end of the current framework programme and the instalment of a new Commission will change some of the parameters of the funding policies and goals.
- The report gives an overview over the EU funding landscape not only for the construction and operation of the EDIC, but also the funding directed towards end users, e.a. Health partnerships. Since in the European data landscape users of the infrastructure are expected to pay for the operational costs incurred on the data infrastructures, it is essential that the funding of the research programmes/partnerships and projects, which form an important class of users for the Genome EDIC, can take this cost into account..

8. Discussion

- EHDS implementation and digitalization in healthcare are key priorities and both present clear opportunities and dependencies that need to be resolved for the Genome-EDIC to fulfil its mission. Specifically there are requirements in terms of authentication and consent management, clear requirements under GDPR, that will be difficult to fulfil in a federated infrastructure without tapping into national and European resources; National eID solutions, and/or European E-wallets and patient/citizen portals in national systems.

- The entire funding ecosystem relevant to Genome-EDIC at a European level is very large and highly complex. Given the political focus on health, beating cancer, digitalization and genomics, which the support for the GDI project in itself is a testament to, there is little doubt that there will be substantial resources available for research and capacity building on those subjects going forward. How to manage this effectively while building up the infrastructure must be carefully handled. While health care and research have a shared goal and vision, there are still marked differences in outlook, incentives and motivation that makes it hard to accommodate a shared approach to funding, priorities and capacity building.
- Genome EDIC is not built in isolation, and it is also not built for a single stakeholder. Because of that, many of the decisions that need to be taken about the funding mechanisms cannot be taken lightly. Good governance is required to address the dependencies internally (In the Genome-EDIC and 1+MG framework) between healthcare and research stakeholders, between member countries and with the Commission. And even more consideration is needed for dependencies between 1+MG/GDI and outside forces such as EHDS, Personalized Medicine initiatives, legal requirements, the political level, interconnection with other research infrastructure and data providers. If the Genome-EDIC is to be long-term sustainable, avenues are needed to constructively address the dependencies that exist on a national level and European level, and a trust framework must be built and open dialogue conducted internally and towards external stakeholders to allow those dependencies to be addressed - to navigate implementation with a focus on what is achievable now and what is desirable over time. It is unwise to push ahead in a particular direction, under the assumption that key dependencies will be resolved retrospectively; doing so carries a huge risk of not achieving the EDIC's mission, mispending of valuable resources, loss of momentum and/or alienating funders and other stakeholders.
- What should clearly be avoided is that different stakeholders have unrealistic expectations of what others can deliver - particularly outside their area of expertise, motivation, funding regime or mandate.
- The Genome-EDIC federated secure processing platform, could be in a unique position at both a national and European level, as an infrastructure that bridges stakeholders across health care, life science research and innovation, and due to the generic nature and scalability of the technical platform it has an enormous potential to be applied to many different needs across this ecosystem. How to unlock that potential and to minimise parallel structures and parallel investments should clearly be addressed with the partners and with the larger stakeholder community.

9. Conclusions & Impact

- The funding schemes identified in this report only provide very limited - if any - funding for the operation of the infrastructure directly. Certainly the EU programmes does not foresee funding of operations of an infrastructure, only support the building up and to some extent

funding for providing "free" resources to users. This needs further investigation to ensure that there is no gap in the work done so far.

- The business model for the Genome-EDIC should accommodate the needs of the European partnerships, since many of the projects funded through the partnership programmes will have user needs that Genome-EDIC will be able to support.
- There does not seem to be any suitable direct funding mechanism for establishing a strong and comprehensive risk management system that will fit the needs in a federated complex digital platform for sensitive data. Further analysis is needed to identify funding avenues for this activity, the establishment of which will significantly impact the go-live date for the infrastructure.

10. Next steps

- The next report (D2.7) on possible sustainability models as learnt from other infrastructures and the evaluation of options is due by December 2024. This work will in large part be based on the findings of the D2.1 report on cost items, The D2.2 report on budget and this D2.6 report on possible sources for funding.
- Investigate further the potential for co-funding the operations of the infrastructure through commissioning of services, either at national or EU level.
- In parallel with this, there is also significant work going on that feeds into the sustainability model:
 - Understanding what services the EDIC will be able to offer at any given time is critically important to manage expectations with funders and users. To this end Pillar I has presented the concept of a Minimal Viable Product: what the infrastructure needs to be able to offer at the moment it becomes operational. The MVP description needs to answer a very simple question - which services can be provided to real users based on real data?
 - Discussing the MVP has revealed substantial differences in perspective across the pillars of the GDI project, and also misunderstandings and misconceptions about what is assumed to be achievable. It is critically urgent to condense the very high level use cases and user stories developed in Pillar III into actionable services that comply with legislation, and can be answered with available data sources and technical capability.
 - The Business Model Canvas presented in this report, will be instrumental in condensing discussions across the GDI project and will hopefully establish a clear path towards implementation of a business model and towards long term sustainability
 - Understanding the different perspectives and expectations for the infrastructure that bridges health and research stakeholders, and developing a working business model and governance at European and at national level needs further considerations. Work has been initiated to support those discussions.
- Identify and engage with relevant EHDS partners on interoperability of platform modules, to
 - ensure the interoperability of the Genome EDIC SPE and the 1+MG catalogue

- Align activities and development of key features for user management and citizen engagement - Authentication tools and Citizen/consent management platform.
- Engagement with key Digital Europe projects, including EUCAIM, establishing synergies and scalability of service platforms.
- Engagement with established EU level health partnerships to develop platforms towards partnership aims - not least Innovative Health Initiative projects.
- Further engagement with EHDS stakeholders at national and EU level is needed in order to explore the potential for the Genome-EDIC to get funding for commissioned services towards EHDS.

11. Appendices

11.1 Business model canvas Questionnaire

Underneath is a representation of the generic Business Model Canvas. It contains nine boxes: Key partnerships, Key activities, Key resources, customer relationships, customer segments, revenue streams and cost structure - and placed at the centre: the value proposition of the business - which value is this business providing and how does that stand out.

The 9 building blocks of the Business Model Canvas

Value proposition

Defining the value the business brings to customers. What value do you deliver to customer/user, in terms of improvements or changes in performance, quality, customization, price/cost reduction, risk reduction, convenience/usability.

- Which of the user's problems are you helping to solve
- Which customer/user needs are you satisfying?
- Which products and services are bundled to satisfy user needs?

Key partners:

Mapping out the most important relationships and collaborations with stakeholders (suppliers, vendors and other partners).

- What is the motivation to partner up with others? Optimization, dependencies?
- Who are the key partners?
- Who are the key suppliers?
- Which key resources are you acquiring from partners?
- Which key activities do partners perform?

Key activities

Activities that must be performed to deliver value and operate successfully.

- What key activities do your value proposition require?
- What are the main distribution channels?
- Customer relations?
- Revenue streams?

Key resources

The vital resources the business needs to operate

- What key resources do your value proposition require?
- What are the main distribution channels?
- Customer relations?
- Revenue streams?

User relations

Understanding the business' relationship with its customers and how to interact with them.

- Which type of relationship do your users expect from you? Direct user support, automated services, self-service, community co-creation.
- Have you segmented users into different groups with differing services? Which? How?

- How do you get buy-in and support from users and funders?

User segments

The different groups of users/customers that the business targets with its products and services.

- For whom are you creating value? Who are the most important customers/users?
- Could you identify different user segments in these groups?

Channels

The different channels, physical and digital, that the business uses to react and interact with customers.

- Through which channels do your users want to be reached?
- How are you reaching them now?

Revenue streams

The different sources of revenue generated from customers - users and/or stakeholders/sponsors)

- For what value are users willing to pay?
- For what are they currently paying?
- How are transactions performed?
- Who actually pays

The various costs that the business incurs to operate)

- What are the most important costs in your business model?
- Which key resources are the most expensive?
- Which key activities are the most expensive?

